

Condition monitoring platform for proactive and reactive operation and maintenance (O&M) with enhanced data analytic functionalities

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Introduction

A key factor important for the future photovoltaic (PV) uptake and the PV value chain is to reduce the Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCoE). This can be achieved by increasing lifetime performance and reducing operating costs through robust condition monitoring offering quality control, safeguarding guarantees and cost-effective operation and maintenance (O&M). Specifically, since monitoring systems can assist to reduce the LCoE of PV, specific novel features based on advanced data analytics need to be included, such as data quality routines (DQRs) providing data sanity and integrity, system health state monitors offering real time operating state information, failure diagnosis through data analysis and other added value services such as performance loss quantification and degradation rate (DR) estimation.

Figure 1: Robust conditioning monitoring system.

Scope

Development of an innovative condition monitoring platform for proactive and reactive O&M with enhanced data analytic functionalities to ensure operational quality and optimize PV energy production.

Results

Sample of the obtained results are illustrated in the figures below:

Figure 2: a) Export of the DQRs showing the amount of missing data in a tested time series form a test-bench PV system in Cyprus, b) System health state detector and c) degradation rate estimation for a test system installed in Cyprus.